

Cross-Country Analysis of BIM Enforcement by the Public Sector

LUIS FELIPE ZULUAGA MOSQUERA

Supervisors:

José Carlos Lino

University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal

Hélder Sousa

University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal

Abstract

BIM has proven its benefits over traditional construction methodologies. The public sector is one of the main benefited from BIM implementation, been considered the largest clients in the industry. Studying how BIM has been adopted on a large scale in different countries around the world then becomes a great resource for benchmarking. To achieve that, this study starts by performing a scoping review to understand how BIM has been enforced globally, and what is considered a BIM mandate based in the literature. The results showed how BIM enforcement change through the passage of time, and the singularities from the context of each country. It was found a gap in the literature regarding BIM mandates worldwide. To fill that gap, a collection of BIM mandates was created and analysed. From the content studied, major approaches in the BIM mandates were observed varying among countries. Also, a list of general elements contained in the mandates was redacted, as to serve as an example to produce BIM mandates. Finally, an online survey was conducted to gather information regarding BIM mandates from professionals in various countries. With the interest from key BIM experts, structured interviews were carried out. From these interviews, insights about proper BIM mandates formulations, considered challenges after introduction of the mandates, and inclusion of open approaches in the mandates, were gathered. Overall, BIM

mandates are a relevant topic that requires further examination, and this study serves as a great resource for further investigation.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/y3emRIiQu6w>

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